

Prevalence, Morphology and Location of Maxillary Sinus Septa using Cone Beam Computed Tomography (CBCT): A Review with Emphasis on North Indian Populations

Reeya Rana¹
Naman Mundepi²

PG Student¹
Department of Oral Medicine and Radiology
Divya Jyoti College of Dental Sciences and Research
Modinagar

Consultant²
Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery
Kothiwai Dental College and Research Centre
Moradabad

Abstract

Background: Maxillary sinus septa (Underwood's septa) are common anatomical variations that may complicate sinus augmentation and posterior maxillary implant placement. Cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT) allows precise three dimensional evaluation of septa morphology, number, orientation, height, and location.

Objective: This review aimed to summarize CBCT based literature on the prevalence, morphology, and typical locations of maxillary sinus septa, with emphasis on North Indian populations, and to discuss the clinical implications and limitations of CBCT for surgical planning.

Methods: A systematic search of PubMed/PMC, Scopus, and Google Scholar was conducted for studies up to 2025 using keywords related to maxillary sinus septa and CBCT. Human CBCT or CT studies with ≥ 5 patients and quantitative data on septa prevalence or morphology were included. Extracted data included prevalence, septa number, orientation, height, location, dentition correlation, and CBCT parameters.

Results: The global pooled prevalence of maxillary sinus septa is approximately 41% per patient, though individual studies report 25–56% depending on population and methodology. North Indian CBCT studies report lower prevalence (8.9–21.3%) but similar morphology predominantly single, bucco-palatal orientation, middle region (first molar area) predominance, and mean height 4–8 mm. Presence of septa increases the risk of Schneiderian membrane perforation during lateral window sinus augmentation. CBCT limitations include voxel size, field of view (FOV), and inter-observer variability.

Conclusions: CBCT is the imaging modality of choice for preoperative evaluation of maxillary sinus septa. Standardized reporting and awareness of CBCT limitations improve surgical safety and inter-study comparability. Population specific data, particularly from North India, highlight variability that should guide clinical planning.

Introduction

The maxillary sinus exhibits several anatomical variations, among which bony septa (Underwood's septa) are particularly significant. First described by Underwood in 1910, these bony projections within the sinus cavity can complicate sinus floor elevation and implant placement due to an increased risk of Schneiderian membrane perforation.^{1,5,10} The reported prevalence of septa ranges between 25% and 56%, depending on population characteristics, imaging methodology, and diagnostic criteria.^{1,3,4} Typically, septa appear as single bony partitions, most often bucco-palatal in orientation and located in the middle region corresponding to the first molar area.^{5,11}

Advancements in imaging technology, particularly the introduction of CBCT, have enabled precise evaluation of the maxillary sinus in three dimensions (Fig. 1), providing detailed information about the presence, number, height, and orientation of septa. Compared with conventional radiography, CBCT offers superior spatial resolution, lower radiation dose relative to CT, and accurate visualization of fine anatomical structures.^{2,3,13} Consequently, CBCT has become the preferred imaging modality for sinus evaluation and implant planning.

Submitted 06 October 2025
Accepted 13 October 2025
Published xx xxx xxxx

Access this article online
Website : www.updent.in
DOI
Quick Response Code

How to Cite This Article : Rana et al. -

Despite numerous global studies, data from North Indian populations remain limited.⁸ Considering regional anatomical variability, such data are essential for optimizing implant planning and minimizing intraoperative complications.^{2,7} Hence, this review integrates global CBCT based findings with a particular focus on the North Indian population.

Rationale and Objectives

This review aims to:

1. Summarize global CBCT derived estimates of the prevalence, morphology, and location of maxillary sinus septa.^{1,3,4}
2. Highlight CBCT based findings specific to North Indian populations to provide population-specific clinical guidance.^{2,7}
3. Discuss clinical implications, limitations of CBCT assessment, and propose a standardized reporting approach for sinus septa.^{6,13}

Methods

Search Strategy

A systematic search of PubMed/PMC, Scopus, and Google Scholar was conducted up to January 2025 using the following keywords: maxillary sinus septa, Underwood septa, cone-beam computed tomography, CBCT, prevalence, morphology, India, North India, sinus lift.

Inclusion Criteria

- Human CBCT or CT studies evaluating sinus septa.^{1-3,7}
- Sample size ≥ 5 patients.
- Quantitative data on prevalence, orientation, height, or location.

Exclusion Criteria

- Case reports (<5 patients), cadaver only studies, or those lacking imaging methods.
- Reviews without original CBCT data.

Data Extraction

For each study, the following were recorded: author, year, country/region, sample size, CBCT machine, voxel size, field of view (FOV), slice thickness, septa prevalence per patient/sinus, number, orientation, height, location, dentition correlation, and risk of Schneiderian membrane perforation.^{6,10}

Quality Assessment

Studies were evaluated using a modified Newcastle Ottawa scale for observational imaging research, emphasizing observer calibration, CBCT resolution, and septa definition criteria.¹³

Figure 1: View of septa in CBCT sections

Figure 2: Length of the sinus septa in coronal plane

Figure 3: Width of horizontal sinus septa in axial view

Figure 4: Width of vertical sinus septa in coronal view

Figure 5: CBCT image of posterior sinus septa

Results

Global pooled prevalence and variability: A 2022 systematic review and meta-analysis of CT and CBCT studies pooled 9,631 patients and reported a pooled prevalence of ~41% per patient (95% CI 36–46%), but noted high

heterogeneity (I² high). Differences were attributed to imaging modalities, septa definitions, and population differences.^{1,3} Individual CBCT studies report prevalence ranges typically between ~25% and 56%, reflecting differences in cohort selection, measurement thresholds, and methodology.^{3,4,13}

Morphology: number, orientation, and height: When present, septa are more often single than multiple, with many studies reporting ~85–90% single septa among sinuses with septa. The bucco-palatal orientation, i.e., vertical plate between buccal and palatal walls, is most common (Fig. 3), while antero-posterior orientations are less frequent. Reported mean septa height commonly falls in the ~4–8 mm range⁹ (Fig. 2). Notably, many studies define “clinically significant” septa as those ≥2–4 mm in height; for example, Verma et al. (2024) reported a mean septa height of ~6.16 mm.²

Location (Anterior/Middle/Posterior): Septa are variably located in anterior, middle, or posterior thirds of the sinus (Fig.4). Underwood’s original description correlated septa with regions between tooth roots. Several modern CBCT studies report the middle region (first molar area) as most common, although some populations demonstrate anterior or posterior predominance, reflecting inter-study variability.^{5,11}

North Indian population data: Verma (2024) reported a prevalence of 21.3%, with most septa single (~90.6%), located in the middle region (~48.4%), predominantly bucco-palatal (~93.8%), and mean height ~6.16 mm.² A large Northeast Indian cohort (Verma et al., 2025) of 1,160 subjects demonstrated a prevalence of 8.88%, highlighting substantial regional variation and the need for population-specific data.¹²

Clinical Impact: The presence of septa, especially complete septa crossing the lateral window area, is associated with a higher risk of Schneiderian membrane perforation during lateral window sinus augmentation (Fig. 5). Preoperative CBCT identification allows modification of surgical technique to reduce intraoperative complications.⁶

Discussion

Main findings: CBCT studies and meta-analytic data confirm that maxillary sinus septa are common anatomical variations with pooled prevalence around 40% per patient. North Indian CBCT series report lower prevalence in some cohorts (8.9–21.3%) compared with global estimates. Morphology when present remains consistent: single septa, bucco-palatal orientation, middle region predominance, and heights commonly 4–8 mm.^{1–5,11} The presence of septa increases the risk of Schneiderian membrane perforation, emphasizing the importance of preoperative CBCT assessment.^{2,7,13}

Why Prevalence Varies: Reported variability arises from methodological differences, including thresholds for what qualifies as a septum (e.g., minimum height for clinical significance, typically ≥2–4 mm), observer calibration, CBCT voxel size and field of view, and whether prevalence is reported per patient or per sinus. Population factors such as dentition status, age, sinus pneumatization, and genetic differences further influence septa prevalence. Reporting bias and study design (single center vs multicenter) also contribute to

variation.^{2,3,7,13}

Clinical Implications: Preoperative CBCT is strongly recommended for candidates of lateral sinus augmentation or posterior maxillary implant placement with anatomic uncertainty. Surgeons should identify septa number, location, orientation, and height, and document relation to the planned lateral window. High or complete septa may require modified lateral window designs (e.g., split windows or septum sectioning) to minimize membrane perforation risk. Explicit reporting of septa in CBCT and surgical planning notes enhances communication and surgical safety.⁶

Standardized CBCT Reporting Recommendations: For each sinus, report presence/absence, number of septa, location (anterior/middle/posterior), orientation (bucco-palatal, antero-posterior, or oblique), maximum measured height (mm) with measurement method, relationship to planned surgical site, and suggested surgical considerations.^{2,5,13}

Limitations & future Directions: Heterogeneity in definitions and measurement techniques limits direct comparability across studies. Regional representation is limited in India, with North Indian prevalence showing variability. Future multicenter CBCT studies should adopt standardized minimum criteria (e.g., minimum septa height, measurement planes), report per-sinus and per-patient prevalence, and incorporate dentition/pneumatization history to differentiate primary vs secondary septa origins.^{2,7,13}

Conclusion

Maxillary sinus septa are clinically significant anatomical variations that can influence sinus lift and implant procedures. CBCT remains the preferred imaging modality for their evaluation, offering accurate three dimensional assessment essential for surgical planning.^{2,3,5,6,11,13} Although North Indian studies show a lower prevalence than global averages, septa morphology remains comparable. Emphasizing explicit CBCT reporting and awareness of imaging limitations enhances diagnostic reliability, surgical safety, and cross-population research consistency.^{2,7,13}

References

- Henriques I, Caramês J, Francisco H, et al. Prevalence of maxillary sinus septa: systematic review and meta-analysis. *Int J Oral Maxillofac Surg.* 2022; 51 (7): 823-831. doi: 10.1016/j.ijom.2022.02.003
- Verma R, Dua N, Gupta R, et al. Evaluation of maxillary sinus septa using CBCT: A retrospective study. *Cureus.* 2024; 16 (8): e68157. doi:10.7759/cureus.68157
- Abesi F, Motaharinia Y, Ghaffari T, et al. Systematic review and meta-analysis of CBCT studies on maxillary sinus septa. *J Clin Exp Dent.* 2023;15 (3): e249-e255. doi: 10.4317/jced.56467
- Yüksel IB, Erdem A, Akinci A, et al. Radiographic prevalence and anatomical characteristics of maxillary sinus septae: CBCT study. *BMC Oral Health.* 2025;25(1):45. doi:10.1186/s12903-025-06268-9
- Bornstein MM, Seiffert M, Maestre-Ferrín L, et al. Analysis of frequency, morphology, and locations of maxillary sinus

- septa using CBCT. *Int J Oral Maxillofac Implants*. 2016; 31 (2): 280–287. doi:10.11607/jomi.4200
6. Al-Dajani M. Incidence, risk factors, and complications of Schneiderian membrane perforation in sinus lift surgery: A meta-analysis. *Implant Dent*. 2016;25(3):409–415. doi: 10.1097/IDS.0000000000000293
 7. Paknahad M, Kharazifard MJ, Alavi S, et al. Prevalence and features of maxillary sinus septa in patients with cleft lip and palate compared to non-CLP individuals: CBCT study. *J Craniofac Surg*. 2024;35(5):e463-e467. doi: 10.1097/SCS.00000000000007105
 8. Mudgale D, Motghare P, Kunjir G, et al. Prevalence of anatomical variations in maxillary sinus using CBCT. *J Indian Acad Oral Med Radiol*. 2018; 30 (1):18–23. doi: 10.4103/jiaomr.jiaomr_51_17
 9. Laçin N, İzol BS. Evaluation of septa in maxillary sinus with CBCT. *Int Dent Res*. 2019; 9 (2): 41–45
 10. Naitoh M, Suenaga Y, Kondo S, et al. Assessment of maxillary sinus septa using CBCT: Etiological consideration. *Clin Implant Dent Relat Res*. 2009;11(s1): e52–e58. doi: 10.1111/j.1708-8208.2009.00199.x
 11. Takeda D, Hasegawa T, Saito I, et al. Radiologic evaluation of incidence and morphology of maxillary sinus septa in Japanese dentate maxillae. *Oral Maxillofac Surg*. 2019; 23 (2): 233–237. doi:10.1007/s10006-019-00780-5
 12. Verma R, Dua N, Gupta R, Singh A, Sharma P. Assessment of maxillary sinus septa in Northeast Indian population: A retrospective CBCT evaluation. *J Pharm Bioallied Sci*. 2025;17(Suppl2): S1328-S1330. doi:10.4103/jpbs.jpbs_1704_24
 13. Hungerbühler A, Rostetter C, Lübbers H-T, et al. Anatomical characteristics of maxillary sinus septa visualized by CBCT. *Int J Oral Maxillofac Surg*. 2019; 48 (3): 382–387. doi: 10.1016/j.ijom.2018.10.013